

FAN, TA'LIM, TEXNOLOGIYA VA ISHLAB CHIQRISH INTEGRATSIYASI ASOSIDA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI

MUSTAQILLIK YILLARIDA MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM TIZIMIDA AMALGA OSHIRILAYATGAN ISLOHOTLAR

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Annotatsiya: Fan va ta'lim sohasida faol mehnat qilayotgan, iqtidorini namoyon etayotgan yosh murabbiylarga uy-joy va turmush tarzini yaxshilashga qaratilgan davlat tomonidan imtiyozli kreditlar ajratib berilmoqda. Bu esa yosh murabbiy va tarbiyachilarni o'z kasbini fidoiysi bo'lib yetishiga, bilim va salohiyatini oshirishga ko'maklashmoqda. Zotan, vazirlik tomonidan qabul qilingan qonun hujjati pedagoglarning o'z kasbiy mahoratlarini oshirishga rag'bat uyg'otgan holda ularni doimiy ravishda moddiy va ma'naviy qo'llab – quvvatlashga zamin yaratgan.

Kalit so'zlar: «Qaldirg'och» «Sog'lom avlod uchun» «Boychechak»-
«Shuhrat» medali «Do'stlik» ordeni

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2019 yil 7 iyundagi 470-sonli qarori bilan tasdiqlangan Nizomga asosan 2020 yilning yanvar, fevral, mart oyining 16-sanasiga qadar 42 ta maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari attestatsiya va davlat akkreditatsiyasidan o'tkazilgan, shundan 41 ta tashkilot akkreditatsiyalanib, 5 yil muddatga o'z faoliyatini yuritish maqomini kafolatlaydigan sertifikatlarni olishdi. Pandemiya sharoitida 2020 yil 16-mart sanasidan ta'lim to'xtatilganligi sababli 31 ta maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarini attestatsiya va Davlat akkreditatsiyasidan o'tkazish 2021 yil rejasiga kiritilgan. **Qonunchilik palatasi tomonidan 2019 yil 22 oktyabrda qabul qilingan Senat tomonidan 2019 yil 14 dekabrda ma'qullangan** "Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya to'g'risida" gi qonunning ijrosini ta'minlash maqsadida Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida ishchi-xodimlar va ota-onalar o'rtasida keng targ'ibot ishlari olib borildi. Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida bannerlar tashkil etildi. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha ta'lim vazirligining 2020 yil 6 oktyabrdagi 03-01-/5-2145-sonli xati asosida boshqarmaning 2020 yil 13 oktyabrdagi 02-12/491-sonli xatiga muvofiq davlat maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari reytingini aniqlash sohasida maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari pedagog xodimlar faoliyati va ta'lim sifati reytingini aniqlash ishlari tashkil etildi. Reyting natijalari boshqarmaning "Ta'lim sifatini tashkil etish va innovatsion texnologiyalarni joriy etish" bo'limi

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tomonidan umumlashtirilib, maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari ta'lim sifati reytingi aniqlandi.¹

Malakali pedagog–murabbiylarning tashabbuskorligi, mashaqatli mehnati har vaqt davlatimiz diqqat nazarida bo'lib kelgan. Viloyatning ustoz murabiylari xalq nazariga tushib, doimo ulug'lanib kelishgan. Chunonchi, meshnat faoliyatida muvaffaqiyatga erishgan bir guruh ustoz pedagoglar Vatanimizning oliy mukofoti va orden medallariga sazavor bo'lganlar. Jumladan, 1919-2020 yilda Karmana tumanidagi «Qaldirg'och» nomli 2-MTM metodis tarbiyachisi Maxfirat Abdullayev 2-darajali “Sog'lom avlod uchun» ordeni, № 3-MTM tarbiyachisi Shamroyeva Gulcheshra va “№ 4 “Boychechak”-MTM tarbiyachisi Rashimova Dildoralar “Shuhrat” medali mukofotlari bilan, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti farmoniga ko'ra Karimova Laylo Saidovna - Navoiy shahridagi Mehribonlik uyi tarbiyachisi “Do'stlik” ordeni bilan taqdirlandi. Qolaversa, 60 ga yaqin o'qituvchi-murabbiylar O'zbekiston Respublikasi Xalq ta'limi vazirligi tomonidan “O'zbekiston Respublikasi xalq ta'limi a'lochisi” ko'krak nishoni va faxriy yorliqlari bilan taqdirlandilar.¹ Bu ularning kamtarona mehnatini davlatimiz tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlab kelayotganini yana bir bor tasdiqlaydi.

Fan va ta'lim sohasida faol mehnat qilayotgan, iqtidorini namoyon etayotgan yosh murabbiylarga uy-joy va turmush tarzini yaxshilashga qaratilgan davlat tomonidan imtiyozli kreditlar ajratib berilmoqda. Bu esa yosh murabbiy va tarbiyachilarni o'z kasbini fidoiysi bo'lib yetishiga, bilim va salohiyatini oshirishga ko'maklashmoqda. Zotan, vazirlik tomonidan qabul qilingan qonun hujjati pedagoglarning o'z kasbiy mahoratlarini oshirishga rag'bat uyg'otgan holda ularni doimiy ravishda moddiy va ma'naviy qo'llab – quvvatlashga zamin yaratgan. Arxiv ma'lumotlari tasdiqlaydiki, yosh o'qituvchilarga har tomonlama ko'mak berish ularni rag'batlantirish maqsadida “Yoshlar yili” munosibati bilan Davlat dasturining 97- 98 bandlariga asosan Navoiy viloyati Hokimligi tomonidan umumtalim va maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalari xodimlariga amaliy yordam ko'rsatilgan. Birgina 2018 yilda 7 nafar yosh mutaxassisga “Ipoteka kreditlari, 8 nafar yosh o'qituvchilarga uy - joy qurish uchun yer uchastkalari, 1 nafar o'qituvchiga (Uchquduq tumanidan) 3 xonali kvartira hujjatlari va kaliti topshirildi.

¹ Navoiy viloyati Maktabgacha ta'lim boshqarmasi joriy arxivi. 2020 yil hisoboti.

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Shuningdek, 10 nafar yosh mutaxassis viloyat hokimining faxriy yorlig'i, 9 nafar yosh mutaxassisga mehnat daftarchalari va esdalik sovg'alari topshirilgan.

Bugunda Xalq ta'limi xodimlari mehnatiga haq to'lashning takomillash-tirilgan tizimiga asosan Prezidentimiz qaroriga ko'ra maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalari tarbiyachilari, pedogoglari va xodimlarining oylik maoshini 2018 yil 1 mart oyidan boshlab 30% oshirish belgilandi. Bu esa soha xodimlariga bo'lgan e'tiborni, ishonchni bildiradi. Ta'lim –tarbiya sohasida nazariya va amaliyot birligini, barkamol avlodi tarbiyalashdek vazifani to'la – to'kis bajarilishini ta'minlaydi. Xulosa shuki, viloyatdagi maktabgacha tarbiya muassasalari pedagog – tarbiyachilari nafaqat yosh avlodni komil inson qilib tarbiyalash, balki o'z ustlarida tinimsiz ishlash, izlanish yo'lida ham jonbozlik ko'rsatib kelmoqdalar.

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